

The Impact of Different Variables on the Three Cell Lines in Cobalamin Deficient Patients in a Tertiary Care Teaching Hospital**Mohammad Zeya Ansari¹, Sameer Kumar Mehta², Kunal Priyadarshi³, Bijaya Mohanty⁴, Ashok Sunder⁵**¹Consultant, Department of General Medicine, Tata Main Hospital, Jamshedpur, Jharkhand²Senior Consultant, Department of General Medicine, Tata Main Hospital, Jamshedpur, Jharkhand³Consultant, Department of General Medicine, Tata Main Hospital, Jamshedpur, Jharkhand⁴Senior Consultant, Department of General Medicine, Tata Main Hospital, Jamshedpur, Jharkhand⁵Chief Consultant & HOD, Department of General Medicine, Tata Main Hospital, Jamshedpur, Jharkhand

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Abstract:**Introduction:** Cobalamin deficiency is a commonly faced issue now days with varying prevalence globally and different aetiological factors. Some of them may be easily correctable like consumption of cobalamin rich diet and avoidance of medications like Metformin and gastric acid lowering agents. This may lead to different clinical and haematological features with unexpected financial burdens.**Aim:** Our study was aimed to observe the effect of age and gender on cobalamin level and the effect of age, gender, and level of cobalamin on the three cell lines.**Method:** We selected a hundred patients after going through the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Their age, gender, serum cobalamin level and haemogram parameters were noted and correlated statistically.**Result:** Out of the hundred patients, we had 58 males, and 42 females and the maximum were in the age between 41 to 60 years (25%). Here, male patients and the elderly had more severe deficiency of cobalamin compared to their counterparts. We observed bi-cytopenia more commonly than isolated anaemia or pancytopenia. Out of the three variables (age, gender, and severity of cobalamin level) only male gender was statistically associated with cytopenia.**Conclusion:** We observed anaemia as the most common cytopenia in cobalamin deficiency and the severity of its deficiency was more in male gender and elderly people. There was no significant association between cobalamin deficiency and the type of cytopenia either in isolation or in combination. As we could see a high percentage of anaemia and bi-cytopenia in cobalamin deficient state, serum cobalamin should be assessed in all those with such cytopenias.**Keywords:** cobalamin, cytopenia, anaemia, bi-cytopenia, pancytopenia.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Vitamin B12 which is also called cobalamin is an essential factor in the synthesis of nucleic acid [1]. It is almost exclusively found in food products of animal origin like liver. It may be deficient in many with or without symptoms and /or signs of its deficiency. This may be attributed either due to lack of proper diet or malabsorptive states. India is home to 20-40% of a vegetarian population; hence diet related deficiency seems to be commoner in our country.

The other causes of Vitamin B12 deficiency are intrinsic factor deficiency, chronic gastritis, H. Pylori infection, blind loop syndrome, transcobalamin II deficiency and fish tape worm infestation. Cobalamin deficiency may present in

multiple ways from a haematological manifestation to a neurological disorder. Haematologically, there may be anaemia, leucopenia, thrombocytopenia, or combination of any of these. Manifestations involving cardiac, cutaneous, and skeletal systems are also noted. The most common hematologic hallmark of B12 deficiency is megaloblastic anaemia. Megaloblastic anaemia of B 12 deficiency is frequently observed in clinical practice but remains underestimated. Sometimes, anaemia may be severe enough to warrant blood transfusion for symptomatic relief. In fact, assessment of pancytopenia now days, includes vitamin B12 and folic acid assay besides other investigations. It has been observed that cytopenia is affected by the

severity of cobalamin deficiency, the lower the level more are the chances of cytopenia [2].

The prevalence rates of cobalamin deficiency range from 2.5% to 60%, differing by age group, gender, and ethnicity [3]. There are studies that have found the impact of age and gender on the severity of cobalamin deficiency. These may directly and /or indirectly affect the three cell lines in the bone marrow and consequently in the peripheral blood picture. According to the recent National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey in the United States, vitamin B12 deficiency among people over the age of 19 in the general population ranges from 3% to 26% depending on the cut-off used, with women more likely to be deficient than men [4]. Similarly, in another study in California a higher prevalence of vitamin B12 deficiency has been found in the elderly and the women compared to their counterparts [5]. In Indian studies the prevalence of cobalamin deficiency is seen to vary between 16-77% [6,7]. Our study is carried out to see the effect of different factors on the type and severity of cytopenia in cobalamin deficient patients.

Aims:

1. To study the correlation of age and gender on the severity of cobalamin deficiency.
2. To study correlation of age, gender, and level of cobalamin deficiency on the three cell lines.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Age above 15 years
2. Cobalamin deficient first report
3. No febrile illness in recent 3 months
4. No known malignancy

Exclusion Criteria

1. Age below 15 years
2. Use of Vitamin B12
3. Pregnancy or breast feeding
4. Known malabsorption syndrome
5. Gastric / Intestinal surgery
6. Blood transfusion within 3 months
7. Alcoholism
8. Iron deficiency
9. Bleeding patients

Material and Methods

This was a retrospective analytical study which was based on data collection from the patients showing cobalamin deficiency over one year duration.

Total number of patients with cobalamin deficiency was 319 in number. But, as per inclusion and exclusion criteria we got 104 cases and for simplification we took a total of 100 cases. Their demography and other clinical parameters were noted from the online record and case sheets. We have defined anaemia in males less than 13 gm/dl while in nonpregnant females it was less than 12 gm/dl as per WHO. After going through literature and other studies we have taken total leucocyte count less than 4000/cmm as leucopenia and platelet count less than 1,50,000/cmm as thrombocytopenia. All thrombocytopenias found in the autoanalyzer were confirmed manually. We observed the changes in cell lines and serum cobalamin level of every patient.

The normal range of serum cobalamin level in our laboratory is 180-914 pg/ml. The severity of cobalamin deficiency has been defined as severe if below 100 pg/ml and moderate above it.

Statistical formulae used

- SPSS
- Mann Whitney U test
- Chi square test
- P-Value <.05 (significant)

Results

As per figure 1, out of the total 100 patients in our study, we found more male patients (58%) than female (42%). Figure 2 depicts that maximum number of patients were in the age group 41-60 years (25%) followed by 61-75 years (23%) while the least were in the age group above 75 years (12%).

In various age groups male predominance was noted except in the patients below 30 years. We observed the co-existing illnesses in our patients who showed presence of vitamin D deficiency (56%), dyspepsia (49%), diabetes mellitus (37%) and hypertension (26%) in decreasing order of importance.

Out of the variables in male and female, age and platelet count were significantly different while cobalamin, haemoglobin percentage and total leucocyte count were not so. But we found male patients having more of severe cobalamin deficiency compared to female patients (p-value <0.02).

Figure 1: Gender distribution

Figure 2: Age-distribution

Table 1: Age group and gender distribution

Age group (in years)	Male (%)	Female (%)
15-30	8	12
31-45	11	9
46-60	14	8
61-75	16	8
Above 75	9	5

Table 2: Correlation of Variables

Variable	All (n)=100	Male(n)=58	Female(n)=42	p-value
Age	Median-54 IQR-34.75	Median-57.5 IQR-30.25	Median-45 IQR-38.25	.03
Cobalamin level	Median-122 IQR-36	Median-112 IQR-31.5	Median-123 IQR-46.26	.11
Haemoglobin	Median-10.55 IQR-3.15	Median-10.8 IQR-2.92	Median-9.8 IQR-3.62	.10
Total Leucocyte count	Median-6.50 IQR-3.2	Median-5.75 IQR-3.4	Median-6.60 IQR-3.5	.12
Platelet count	Median-204X10 ³ IQR-210X10 ³	Median-128X10 ³ IQR-185X10 ³	Median-238X10 ³ IQR-239X10 ³	<.001

Table 3: Correlation of severity of cobalamin deficiency and gender

Cobalamin level in pg/ml	Male (%)	Female (%)	p-value
≤100	25	9	.02
>100	33	33	

Table 4: Comparison of age group with cobalamin deficiency and cytopenia

Age Group (In years)	Cobalamin Level –in pg/ml (Mean±Sd)	Iso-lated Anaemia)	Iso-lated Leuko-penia	Isolated thrombo-cytopenia	Anaemia with leu-kopenia	Anaemia with throm-bocytopenia	Pancytopenia
15-30	125.25±23.35	10%	0%	1%	0%	6%	3%
31-45	120.70±20.05	4%	0%	1%	0%	10%	5%
46-60	121.08±30.59	5%	0%	0%	2%	11%	4%
61-75	121.47±28.03	6%	1%	1%	1%	8%	7%
>75	101.75±27.32	1%	1%	1%	0%	5%	6%
Total		26%	2%	4%	3%	40%	25%

On comparing different age groups, it has been noted that severity of cobalamin deficiency was more in elderly with the mean value 101.75(SD=27.32).

When we observed the pattern of cytopenia, isolated anaemia was mostly seen in the age group 15-30 years and 61-75 years while anaemia with thrombocytopenia was maximum (27%) below the age of 60 years. But pancytopenia prevalence was

almost same below 60 years (12%) and above it (13%).

It has been observed that anaemia with thrombocytopenia was the most common cytopenia (40%) followed by isolated anaemia (26%) and pancytopenia (25%) in decreasing order. On the other hand, isolated leukopenia was seen in few (2%) cases only.

Table 5: Correlation of age, gender, and level of B12 with cytopenia

Factors	Percentage of patients with cytopenia	Percentage of patients without cytopenia	p-value
Age group			
15-30	16	20	.92
31-45	14	20	
46-60	21	25	
61-75	24	23	
Above 75	11	12	
Gender	M		
F	56	2	<.001
	33	9	
Level of cobalamin			
≤ 100	32	2	.24
>100	56	10	

The impact of age, gender, and severity of cobalamin deficiency on cytopenia was observed and calculated. Out of the three, only gender was significantly associated with cytopenia where male was affected more compared to female (table - 5).

Table 6: Correlation of type of cytopenia with Gender

Cytopenia type	Male (%)	Female (%)	p-value
Isolated Anaemia			
• Yes (26%)	15	11	.97
• No	43	31	
Isolated Leukopenia			
• Yes (2%)	1	1	.81
• No	57	41	
Isolated Thrombocytopenia			
• Yes (4%)	3	1	.48
• No	55	41	
Bi-cytopenia (Anaemia with Leukopenia)			
• Yes (3%)	1	2	.37
• No	57	40	
Bi-cytopenia (Anaemia with thrombocytopenia)			

• Yes (40%)	23	17	.93
• No	35	25	
Pancytopenia			
• Yes (25%)	15	10	.81
• No	43	32	
Total anaemia			
• Yes (94%)	54	40	.65
• No	4	2	
Total thrombocytopenia			
• Yes (69%)	41	28	.66
• No	17	14	

When we separately observed the type of cytopenia in respect to gender, prevalence of anaemia was maximum (94%) followed by thrombocytopenia (69%). Similarly, prevalence of anaemia with thrombocytopenia was much more (40%) compared to anaemia with leucopenia (3%). Isolated thrombocytopenia and leucopenia were present in the least (4% and 2% respectively). None of the cytopenia, either in isolation or in combination were significantly different in between the two genders (table-6).

Discussion

We see different types of cytopenias in our clinical practice both in outdoor and indoor set up. It can be due to many different reasons, cobalamin deficiency being one of them. Often, it can be associated with etiological factors like a febrile illness or a drug and resolves spontaneously within a week or more. But many a times the cytopenia persists longer than expected. In that case, further investigations are warranted, wherein we may see cobalamin deficiency to be the possible cause. When we start oral or injectable replacement for this, we see complete reversal of cytopenia with rise in serum cobalamin level. So, if we assess cobalamin level in the beginning itself, many unnecessary investigations may be avoided, and early etiological diagnosis would lead to timely corrective therapy and its expected response. It was with this idea, this study was undertaken, and the observations noted.

The gender distribution in our study showed male predominance similar to another study [8] in contrast to the other one done by N. Praneetha et al [9]. The severity in deficiency of cobalamin may not be gender specific. In a cross-sectional study, cobalamin deficiency was more in male group which was hypothesized to be due to genetic variations as it could not be correlated with diet or estrogen [10]. This was like our study showing male predominance with severe cobalamin deficiency than female. Although, in general female population is affected by cobalamin deficiency more due to poor diet intake despite more requirement [4,17]. There can be different impact of age, gender, and cobalamin deficiency on the three cell lines.

Anaemia was seen with no statistically significant difference in the male and female patients in our study which resembles the finding of Azimi et al [11]. There was no significant difference in presence of leukopenia between the genders in our study similar to Azimi et al but it was in contrast to the findings noted by Samson JC et al & N. Praneetha et al [8,9,11].

When we observed thrombocytopenia, it was significantly prevalent in our study similar to Samson JC et al & N. Praneetha but in contrast to the studies by Azimi et al [8,9,11]. The factors leading to such differences could not be ascertained or contemplated. The effect of severity of cobalamin deficiency on the cell lines was noted with more of bi-cytopenia and pancytopenia in the age group above 60 years. This could be due to the lower levels of cobalamin compared to people in the age below this age. Similarly, the elderly population might be having comorbid conditions and could be on multiple medications that may lead to poor food intake and/or decreased absorption capability of intestinal tract leading to cobalamin deficiency [12,13].

Although, we could see 16% of total patients with pancytopenia almost similar (12.7%) to another Indian study [14], in other study it was lesser [15]. Our study shows that most common cytopenia noted is anaemia followed by thrombocytopenia but none of the cytopenias (either in isolation or in combination) were significantly different between male and female.

Although, bi-cytopenia and pancytopenia were more prevalent in people above age 60 years but when compared with those without cytopenia, there was no significant difference amongst them. In another study the lower was the level of cobalamin, more was the prevalence of bi-cytopenia and pancytopenia [2]. Prevalence of isolated thrombocytopenia caused by cobalamin deficiency is a rare phenomenon [16] and with the same expectation our study also showed it to be quite low (4%). It is seen that megakaryocytes do not mature adequately in the deficiency of cobalamin leading to decreased production of platelets.

When we observed the presence of cytopenia irrespective of its type, it is noted to be more prevalent in the male group with statistical significance (p -value $<.05$). However, there was no difference in the type of cytopenia when compared between the two. The possible explanation here could be that there were more patients above age 60 years in males having more of severe cobalamin deficiency. In a study there was more prevalence of explained cytopenia in female subjects in contrast to unexplained cytopenia that was more in male, but it could not be connected or associated with any of the factors in the demographic profile of the subjects. Although, unexplained cytopenia was thought to be linked with some genetic characteristics as it showed racial preference [17]. Hence, our study could be the starting point for further research on multifactorial impact on the three cell lines in cobalamin deficient subjects.

Conclusion

We found that male gender and elderly people were more severely affected with cobalamin deficiency than their counterparts. It has been observed that anaemia was the most common cytopenia followed by thrombocytopenia and pancytopenia in that order which was statistically insignificantly different between the two genders. The level of serum cobalamin was not showing differential effect on the three cell lines. As anaemia and thrombocytopenia may be caused and/or worsened by cobalamin deficiency, its timely corrections may prevent the development of symptomatic and severe cytopenia.

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